

ANALYSIS OF MARITIME COMMUNITY ROOTS IN INDONESIA FOR ARISING THE INTEREST OF INDONESIAN YOUTH GENERATION IN THE MARITIME FIELD

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Abstract:

Indonesia is known as the largest maritime and archipelagic country in the world which 70% of its territory consisting of sea. It makes some islands in Indonesia are separated by the sea. However, it does not become the barrier for connecting one island to the other islands. In this case, the mode of sea transportation has the important roles and very closely related for connecting these islands. The maritime triumphs began to setback after the Demak kingdom and its junk fleet was defeated by the Portuguese fleet in Malacca strait and also since the invasion of VOC fleet in the colonial era, those two factors caused the descent of maritime glory and the new Mataram kingdom no longer had its fleet. At that time, the character assassination to foster interest of maritime field from generation to generation had decreased significantly with a lack of utilizing that wealth. By looking at the chronologies mentioned previously, the researchers tend to observe from the psychological aspect, the reason why does it happen. The objectives of this study are 1) to find out the factors which causes the decline of the youth generation's interest toward the "nawacita" or the dream of maritime field, 2) to find out how to increase the youth generation's interest toward "nawacita" or dream of maritime field, and 3) to find out the youth generation's interest related to the values of maritime characters. This study is a qualitative research which taking teenage respondents of senior high school grade. Whereas, the data collection techniques used in this study are interview and observation which are conducted to the respondents. After the data is obtained, the data processing techniques used are qualitative analysis techniques. The results of the study are the causative factors of the

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youth generation's interest decline in the aspiration of the maritime field. There are two factors founded, namely 1) internal factors, factors which are originated from the self-individual aspect such as concentration, curiosity, motivation and needs, 2) the external factors, factors which are originated from the outside of individual aspects such as the influence of the surrounding, influence of the social environment, factors of the family environment, and factors of the school environment.

Keywords: interest, maritime, young generation

1. Introduction

Indonesia is known as the largest maritime and archipelagic country in the world which 70% of its territory consisting of sea. It makes some islands in Indonesia are separated by the sea. However, it does not become the barrier for connecting one island to the other islands. In this case, the mode of sea transportation has the important roles and very closely related for connecting these islands.

As a maritime country, Indonesia has enormous potencies for bringing in foreign exchange in processing sources which are originated from the maritime area starting from the sea with all the wealth inside and its sea transportation in this case is ships which connecting one island to another within the country in the frame unity of the Republic of Indonesia and even between other countries.

Since the ancient times the maritime spirit with inter-island, sailing and trade had developed using various types of traditional vessels and boats. Moreover, the voyage and trade was expanded not only went to the islands of Indonesia but also to the outside of the country such as expedition of cinnamon as stated in the famous Borobudur temple relief with junk boats that had sailed to Madagascar up to Ghana, the famous Javanese junk in the royal era Demak kingdom, and the Majapahit kingdom sailed to Japan.

On the contrary, the receding of their role was later due to the retread of a large maritime-based empire such as Sriwijaya and Majapahit as well as the kingdom of Demak and the emergence of small kingdoms based on land. The development got worse after the process of conquest by foreign powers, Western countries such as Portugal, Spain and the Netherlands took place, which made the attention of the maritime sector and the importance of the role of the sea waning. This continued until the period of foreign powers could be expelled from the archipelago, or the Indonesian state, after it was formed (independent), maritime sector began to get attention during the reign of President Sukarno with the emergence of the Djuanda Declaration on 13 December 1957.

The attention to the maritime sector is getting bigger and well-planned, with the rise of Abdurrahman Wahid as the 4th president of the Republic of Indonesia, replacing Habibie, by appointing a minister of marine affairs, under a civil technocrat, Sarwono Kusumaatmaja, who unites the maritime sector with fisheries. The next civilian president, Megawati Soekarnoputeri, gave more attention, continuing what Ir.

Soekarno, the first President of the Republic of Indonesia had shown in the Djuanda Declaration of December 3, 1957. Ir. Soekarno in the early 1960s had actually implemented the importance of maritime sector policies, with his steps to make the Indonesian Navy (ALRI) as a major force in the region, through his choice to develop the power of the marines, Megawati's replacement, a new leader with a military background. Susilo Bambang Yudhoyono (SBY), seemed to restore the army role as the most important element in the Indonesian Armed Forces (Tentara Nasional Indonesia - TNI), during his two years of government, reactivating the military's territorial role, in addition to extending several positions of Endriartono Sutarto, a general with an army background as TNI Commander. Giving priority to the land sector and the role of the Army in national development ended after the re-rise of the civilian regime to the stage of power, namely Joko Widodo with his sea highway program, as Megawati wished in the previous period to return the Indonesian to be the great maritime nation as it was in the previous time.

2. Statements of the Problems

In the Soeharto government, it made a 'blunder' by issuing a policy of ship scrapping over the age of 25 years. It made Indonesian ships forced to retire. The policy caused the maritime sector in Indonesia retreated.

Such developments create complications in the prospect of regional development in the foreseeable future, especially during the administration of Joko Widodo, this regime realizes that as maritime nations must start to rise as a great force through maritime power that has begun to fade since the fall of the kingdom of Demak and the rose of the new Mataram kingdom which began to be oriented towards agrarian power and VOC power which took over the power of the maritime kingdom in Indonesia which once ruled the ocean and dominated the trade power with its sea lanes, based on those reason, the devotion as a maritime nation should be planted especially for the young generation of Indonesia so that the Indonesian nation can always be counted as a great maritime nation like the era of Srivijaya, Majapahit and Demak.

From the above explanation, the statements of the problems in this study include:

- 1) What are the factors causes of the decline of the youth generation's interest in maritime field toward the "nawacita" ideals?
- 2) What are the techniques for increasing the interest of the youth generation toward the "nawacita" of maritime field?
- 3) What about the interest of the youth generation in the values of soul character of maritime nowadays?

2.1 The Objectives of the Research

- 1) To find out the factors which cause the decline of the youth generation's interest toward the "nawacita" or the dream of maritime field.

- 2) To find out how to increase the youth generation's interest toward "nawacita" or dream of maritime field.
- 3) To find out the interest of the younger generation in the values of maritime character.

2.2 Benefits of Research

There are basic things, which are directed as implications of this study, namely:

- 1) This research will provide a very valuable contribution to the policy makers of maritime content related to the curriculum specifically which can foster the sense of love and pride as a maritime nation in Indonesia which can finally restore the value of soul character of maritime to the young generation.
- 2) This research contribute to find some solutions to figure out maritime problems in the future by generating character values of the younger generation to raise the interest in the maritime aspirations, so that in the future it is hoped that the young generation of Indonesia can be a great nation in maritime affairs and have a world recognition.
- 3) This research provide a very significant contribution to the community about how maritime devotion is, so that the Indonesian people can be able to manage all the maritime resources as much as possible and can support the program in the maritime sector so hopefully it can make progress to the community both at the regional and national levels.

3. Literature Review

In the dictionary of psychology, Chaplin in Prima (2011: 7) states that interest can be interpreted as follows:

- a) an attitude that goes on and on giving a pattern to;
- b) feelings that state that a work activity or object is valuable or meaningful to the individual;
- c) it is a condition or a set of motivations that demand behavior toward a particular direction.

Interest is a predisposition, tendency, or a feeling reaction that goes on and on which patterned a person's attention so as to make him become selective towards the object of interest. According to Hurlock (1995: 117), interest is divided into 3 aspects, namely:

- a) Cognitive aspects. Based on personal experience and what was learned both at home, school and society and various types of mass media.
- b) Affective aspects. Concepts that build cognitive aspects, interest expressed in attitudes toward activities generated by interest. Developing from personal experience from the attitude of the important person, namely parents, teachers and peers to activities related to those interests and from the attitudes expressed or implied in various forms of mass media on the activity.

- c) Psychomotor aspects. Run smoothly without the need for more thought, the order is right. But progress is still possible so flexibility and excellence increase even though it runs slow.

John Dewey (in Harackiewicz, 2002) described interest as “*being engaged, engrossed, or entirely taken up with*” an activity, object, or topic (Dewey, 1913, p. 17). More contemporary interest theorists have characterized interest as being both a psychological state, and a process that emerges over time through the interaction between an individual and an activity or topic (Hidi & Baird, 1986; Renninger, 2000). Individual interest is more enduring, and trait-like, and persists over time. It can be considered a disposition that an individual takes with them from one context to the next.

Interest is often thought of as a process that contributes to learning and achievement. That is, being interested in a topic is a mental resource that enhances learning, which then leads to better performance and achievement (Hidi, 1990). Indeed, research has demonstrated that both situational and individual interest promote attention, recall, task persistence, and effort (Ainley, Hidi, & Berndorff, 2002; Hidi, 1990; Hidi & Renninger, 2006). In their meta-analysis of over 150 studies that examined the relationship between interest and performance,

The factors that influence the interest are as follows:

- a) The factor owner urge (encouragement from the inside) Stimulation that comes from the environment or scope in accordance with the wishes or come from the environment or scope in accordance with the wishes or needs of someone will easily generate interest
- b) The factor of social motives (motives in the social environment) A person's interest in objects or things, besides things influenced by factors from within the human being are also influenced by social motives.
- c) The factor of emotional, these feelings and emotions factors have an influence on the object, for example, a successful trip that is used by an individual in a particular activity can arouse feelings of pleasure and can increase the enthusiasm or strong interest in the activity. Conversely, failure experienced will cause someone's interest to develop.

The types of interests can be classified into four types, namely:

- a) Expressed interest is an interest which is expressed by asking the subject to declare or write down activities both in the form of tasks and not the tasks that are liked and most disliked. For example, someone might say that he was interested in creating a building design.
- b) Manifest interest is an interest expressed by observing or making observations directly on the activities carried out by the subject or by knowing his hobbies. For example, someone plays an active role in social organizations, music groups, and so on.
- c) Tested interest is expressed interest that is used as a way to deduce from the results of answers to objective tests given, high values on an object or problem usually show a high interest in it.

- d) Inventoried interest is interest expressed by using standardized tools, which usually contain questions that are addressed to the subject whether he is happy or unhappy about a number of activities or an object being asked.

Factors that influence interest growth. Factors that influence the interest growth are divided into 5 as follows: 1) motivation and ideals, 2) attitude towards an object, 3) family, 4) facilities, and 5) social friends (Crow & Crow, 1958).

To find out someone's interest can be done by paying attention to what he asks, what is discussed at certain times, what he reads and what he is drawing or painting spontaneously. In the opinion of E.B. Harlock quoted by S.P. Sukartini (1986; 65), analysis of interest can be done on the following matters:

- a) The desire to know or have something that interests him;
- b) The objects or activities he likes;
- c) Types of activities to achieve things that are liked;
- d) Efforts to realize the desire, feeling happy about something that interests him.

Potential - potential that exists in the younger generation that needs to be developed as follows:

- a) Idealism and Critical Power. Sociologically, the younger generation has not been established in the existing order, so that it can see shortcomings in the order and is naturally able to find new ideas.
- b) Dynamics and Creativity. The idealism of the younger generation causes them to have the potential for dynamism and creativity, namely the ability and willingness to make changes, renewal, and refinement of existing deficiencies or express new ideas.
- c) Courage to take risks. Changes and updates, including development, contain the risk of being missed, hampered or failed. The younger generation can be involved in risky businesses.
- d) Optimism and Passion. Failure does not discourage the younger generation. The optimism and enthusiasm of the enthusiasm of the young generation is the driving force to try more advanced.
- e) Attitude of Independence and Pure Discipline. The young generation has the desire to always be independent in their attitudes and actions. The attitude of independence needs to be complemented by a pure awareness of discipline so that they can be aware of reasonable and tolerant boundaries.
- f) Educated. Even though taking into account dropout factors, overall both in the qualitative sense and in the quantitative sense, the younger generation is relatively more educated because of the more open learning opportunities of their predecessor generation.
- g) Diversity in Unity and Unity. The diversity of the young generation is a reflection of the diversity of our society. Such diversity can be an obstacle if lived in a narrow and exclusive manner
- h) Patriotism and Nationalism. Fertilizing a sense of pride, love, and participating in having a nation and state among the younger generation needs to be

encouraged because in turn it will strengthen the spirit of service and their readiness to defend and defend the NKRI from all forms of threats.

- i) Attitude of the Knights. The purity of idealism, courage, the spirit of dedication and sacrifice and a high sense of social responsibility are elements that need to be nurtured and developed among the Indonesian young generation as defenders and enforcers of truth and justice for society and the nation.
- j) Ability to Mastery Science and Technology. The young generation can play an effective role in the framework of developing science and technology if it can be functionally developed as a Transformer and Dynamics towards a more backward environment in the science and education and application of technology, both advanced and simple.

The definition of maritime that has been known by the public is to show the activities in the sea related to shipping and trade, so that activities in the sea that involve exploration, exploitation or fishing are not maritime affairs.

Based on the review of the history of various kingdoms in the archipelago, Indonesia is actually a maritime character. However, the character of maritime is now no longer exist, some people have consideration, to be a strong, respected and be a reputable nation in the world, Indonesia must return to maritime insight rather than land minded.

4. Research Methods

4.1 Population

The population in this study took respondents as many as 6 people who met the requirements or were considered representative. The criteria of the respondents are as follows:

- a) Grade XI senior high school students
- b) The average ages are 16 - 17 years old.
- c) Able to provide answers related to the questions asked.
- d) Physical and spiritual health

4.2 Data collection technique

- a) Interview
- b) Observation

4.3 Sources of the Data

Data is obtained from two sources, namely primary data sources and secondary data sources.

- a) Primary data source. Primary data sources are respondents or people who are directly involved with the object of this research. In this case, the data is obtained directly from the source, namely the scholarship recipient student.

- b) Secondary data source (Istiyanto, 2005, p.38). Secondary data sources are reports, documents, brochures, library books that contain discussion about the object of research, meaning that the author obtains information indirectly.

4.4 Data analysis

Data analysis according to Patton (in Moleong, 2003: 103) in (Yulia, 2008: 48) is a process of organizing data, sorting data into patterns and categories of basic descriptions so that themes can be found and working hypotheses can be formulated as suggested so that information can be obtained deep about the objects to be studied.

After the data is processed, then the next step is to analyze the data which the function is as a tool to draw the expected conclusions, it means that it will be able to answer the problems which have been formulated. Analysis of the data used in this study is qualitative analysis methods. This analysis contains detail description (describing) and size of something that will be investigated and experienced by researchers in the field (Faisal, 1990: 82 in Yulia, 2008: 48). Process and analysis of data starts from the results of observations, the results of interviews then classified and sorted through to presenting it.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Results of the Research

Based on the results obtained from the data analysis and respondents, it was showed the factors that influence the interest of the young generation in the maritime world consist of two factors, namely internal factors and external factors.

From the first respondent, the factors that caused the decline of the interest were external factors, there are some external factors derive from the family environment, where the stepfather of the respondent did not agree that his child became a sailor. Meanwhile, from the second respondent, it can be seen that the factors which influence the young generation's interest in the maritime world are external factors, namely socio-cultural information. From the third respondent, it appeared that the factors that influence the interest of young generation in the maritime world are internal factors, namely the willingness of the respondents to give more time and attention to their families, because when they become seafarers, they will have less and limited time to stay with their family. From the data obtained on respondents 4, the factors that influence the interest of young people in maritime fields are external factors, namely the influence of the surrounding environment, where the influence is obtained from the closest person of the respondent.

In accordance with the results obtained in the study, the most influencing factor that affects the interest of the younger generation in the maritime world is environmental factors. Environmental factors in this case are the family environment, for instance is the support of the family.

Techniques to Increase the Interest of the Young Generation toward the spirit of "Nawacita" (Joy) of Maritime Affairs are as follows:

- 1) Increase the capacity and knowledge of teachers, especially in the maritime field. It can be realized only if the teachers already have the capacity and knowledge toward the maritime field, so that they can provide and include learning content regarding the knowledge in the maritime field to their students.
- 2) Implementing Maritime Thematic Curriculum at schools. Maritime Thematic Curriculum should be given to children from an early age. When children start to school in Paud or TK (kindergarten), to enhance children's interest for the maritime field can be started by introducing some maritime professions, transportation tools, images of marine biota and environment that can be fulfilled with some educational properties in the form of ships or any other properties related to the maritime field. Hopefully, when the children have already had a good perception of the maritime world, someday, when they grow up they will be interested to be a seafarer or sailor.
- 1) Cultivating Knowledge about Maritime in the Family Environment. Family is an early education institution for a child, for this reason the role of family members is needed to help educate and foster knowledge of the children to shape their love toward the maritime field. If in the family has been instilled a sense of love for the maritime world, it will increase their curiosity to learn more and further rise up their sense of love in the maritime world
- 2) Repair and provide good and proper protection to seafarers. Profession of a seafarer has promising future, because it has been known that seafarers can earn much money from their duty. However, when they have their duty off, they cannot get salary. For this reason, it is necessary to provide guarantees for them to get the side incomes by doing some other jobs related to their skills and also give them health protection. It was done with the aim of increasing the sense of love and interest for the maritime field
- 3) Improve the education system during the learning period. This can be done by providing guarantees for the students who stay in the dormitory by ensuring that there is a burdensome education system for them.

6. Recommendations

The further research is recommended to explore more deeply about other factors that influence the increasing interest of the younger generation in the maritime world by adding other factors,

For Maritime Education Institutions, it is expected to be able to make improvements to the education system, curriculum and regulations during learning process, including the dormitory roles.

Parents also need to monitor their children toward their children's new environment and society.

7. Conclusion

Based on the results of the research, then some conclusions can be taken as follows:

- 1) Factors that cause the decline of young generation's interest in "nawacita" (dream or joy) of the maritime world are divided into two factors, including:
 - a) Internal factors, it is some factors which are originated from the individual aspect, it can be: concentration, curiosity, motivation and needs.
 - b) External factors, it is some factors that derived from the outside of the individual aspect such as the influence of the surrounding environment, the influence of the social environment and relationships, the family environment, and factors of the school environment.

In this study, the most emergent factors that influence the decline of the young generation's interest in maritime field are external factors, especially the influence of the family environment and social environment.

- 2) Techniques to increase the interest of the young generation in maritime dreams can be done by:
 - a) Increase the capacity and knowledge of teachers, especially in the maritime field
 - b) Incorporate maritime thematic curricula at schools
 - c) Cultivating Knowledge about maritime in the Family Environment
 - d) Repair and provide clearer protection to seafarers
 - e) Improve the education system during learning process

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The author is a lecturer of Politeknik Maritim Negeri Indonesia, as a lecturer the activities which are carried out must be related to the Tri Dharma of Higher Education, besides teaching, other activities are complete two other dharma in the form of research and community service. The author's educational background is psychology, but in the past 7 years the author has worked in the maritime institution and interested in exploring something related the maritime world, which encouraged researchers to conduct research in the maritime world.

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